

ENSO Impact on Weather and Wave Conditions at Wave Energy Test Site, Hawaii

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Hawaii has a complex wave climate due to its mid-Pacific location and massive archipelago. The US Navy Wave Energy Test Site (WETS) on the east shore of Oahu is open to trade wind waves from the subtropical ridge and seasonal swells generated by extratropical cyclones in the North Pacific as well as severe seas from passing subtropical systems (such as cold fronts and Kona storms) and tropical cyclones. These synoptic and mesoscale weather systems provide diversified wave conditions at WETS with strong seasonal and inter-annual variations. The local waves and weather activities are closely connected to the global climate. Previous studies have focused on the "local" wave climate and energy resources at WETS based on the buoy measurements and wave hindcast. However, the global climate's impact on local waves and weather is not fully understood, despite its importance for operation and planning. In particular, in the wintertime, energetic swells from the North Pacific and high winds from passing cold fronts could hinder site maintenance, including Wave Energy Converter deployments and retrievals.

As a pilot study, we examine the historical weather catalog and wave hindcast to investigate the impact of the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the most prominent climate mode in the Pacific, on the winter weather and wave activity at WETS. During the ENSO positive phase - El Niño, the warmer sea surface temperature (SST) in the central and eastern Pacific can move the Jetstream eastward and strengthen and shift extratropical cyclones (ETCs) equatorward in the North Pacific. There are 40% more cold front events in Hawaii in El Niño than in La Niña years. The associated strong winds and high surfs can increase the risks of shipboard operations at the site. In addition, the monthly average and variability for significant wave height at WETS follow the trend of the ENSO index with a correlation coefficient above 0.8, indicating the strong modulation of ENSO in the winter swell activities. This provides a basis for future development of the wave forecast at WETS in sub-seasonal and seasonal scales, given the robust predictability of ENSO with 6-12 months of lead time. The long-term forecast will benefit decision-making for better preparation and planning of major operations.